

Evaluation of Ethiopian Black Cumin (*Nigella Sativa L.*) Accessions for Yield and Yield Related Characters at Kulumsa, South-Eastern Ethiopia

¹ Kedir Jaletto Bento*, ¹ Gizaw Wegayehu, ¹ Demis Fikre

¹ Kulumsa Agricultural Research Center (KARC), Asella, P.O. Box 489, Ethiopia

*Corresponding author: Kedir Jaletto Bento

Kulumsa Agricultural Research Center (KARC), Asella, P.O. Box 489, Ethiopia

Abstract

A field experiment was conducted to evaluate the performance of black cumin accessions for their agronomic, yield and yield related performance at the Kulumsa Agricultural Research Center in 2020 and 2021. Twenty two black cumin accessions, including local and standard checks, were assessed in a 4×6 alpha-lattice design with two replications. The combined analysis of variance showed a highly significant (P Twenty-two < 0.01) difference was revealed for all studied traits except a significant difference ($P < 0.05$) was recorded for plant height. The mean values for days to 50% flowering, plant height (cm), number of primary branches per plant, number of secondary branches plant-1, number of pod plant-1, number of seed pod-1, seed yield plant-1 (g), and seed yield (kg ha-1) ranged from 88.75-95.75, 57.45-63.85 cm, 4.85-6.4, 10.10-14., 14.45-23.05, 87.05-116.75, 1.87–3.5 g, and 392.81–881.98 kg ha-1, respectively. Among the tested accessions, twelve accessions recorded a mean seed yield that ranged from 743.33 kg ha-1 to 881.98 kg ha-1. Consequently, those materials could be advanced to the national variety trial after testing the accessions for their olio resin and essential oil contents. To check their performance, those landraces should be tested across potentially growing areas of the country.

Keywords: landraces, traits, number of pod, quality, seed yield

1. Introduction

Black cumin (*Nigella sativa L.*) is one of the most important annual seed spice and medicinal herbs, which could be found in every market in Ethiopia. It is a flowering plant that belongs to the family Ranunculaceae (Weiss, 2002; Goreja, 2003; Habtewold et al., 2017) and originated in the Eastern Mediterranean, Southern Europe, West Asia, and Egypt but is widely cultivated in, Japan, China, India, Sri Lanka, Bangladesh, Afghanistan, Pakistan, Egypt, Iran, Iraq, Syria and Turkey (Kokdil et al., 2006; Cheikh Rouhou et al., 2007; Shewaye, 2011; Samima et al., 2017; Kahaliw et al., 2021). Black cumin is named by its different names in various countries; black cumin has different names given in different regions different names like “Tikur azmud” smut (Amharic), Gurraacha habasudu, abosuda, nudge guracha, gurati, gurra (Gallinia), aaf (Kefa), awosetta (Tigrinia) (Jansen, 1981). It is grown in the highlands (1500 to 2500 m.a.s.l.) of Amhara, Oromia, and Southern Nations and Nationalities People’s (SNNP) regions and is usually cultivated using residual moisture (Birhanu et al., 2015; Hailemichael, 2016; Herms et al., 2015). The national average productivity of black cumin was reported to be 0.79 t ha⁻¹, which is below the world average productivity (2.2 t ha⁻¹) (Habtewold et al., 2017). Black cumin contains essential macro and micronutrients which play vital roles as structural and functional components of metalloproteins and enzymes in the living cells and that is why it can give us medicinal value. (Ansari et al., 2004). Ethiopian black cumin varieties contain up to 50% thymol in their seed, a monocyclic phenolic compound that makes black cumin valuable for medicinal value (Ansari et al., 2004; Ashraf and Orooj, 2006; Black et al., 2006; Bardideh et al., 2013; Merga et al., 2018; Demis et al., 2023). The crop is used to flavor foods, prepare oil for perfumes and medicinal purposes, provide a source of income, and diversify crops (Teshome and Anshiso, 2019; Wubshet and Desalegn, 2019). It is used to make 'Berbere' for the preparation of traditional Ethiopian stews such as 'wot' and preservation of butter (Mengistu et al, 2021) and for reducing the hotness of pepper powder (Hedberg, 1996). Traditionally, farmers have treated various diseases with the help of *nigella sativa*. For example, black cumin seed mixed with honey has been shown to heal stomach aches (Tesfa et al., 2017; Diwakar et al., 2018). Scholars have been reported

that black cumin used to treat animal and human ailments, anti-microbial drugs, and antioxidant and improves memory ability (Sahak et al., 2016; Abdallah, 2017; Tavakkoli et al., 2017; Paseban et al., 2019; Mengistu and Wegayehu, 2023). In Ethiopia, black cumin, white cumin, pepper, paprika, turmeric, fenugreek, garlic, coriander, ginger, cardamom, and basil are spices grown for consumption and commercial purposes and considered top spice producers and consumer countries, ranking first and seventh in Africa and the world, respectively (Tesfa et al., 2017; Anonymous, 2019).

Despite the fact, black cumin is the most important seed spice in our daily usage, lack of access to improved varieties; improper crop management, high weed incidence, disease, insect damage, inadequate plant population, inadequate postharvest handling, and a lack of market-oriented production are contributed for low productivity and production of the crop. Among the problems, the low yields are mainly due to access to improved varieties and the use of local varieties (Assefa et al., 2015). Therefore, the objective of this study was to evaluate black cumin accessions for agronomic, yield and yield related characters and advance the high yielders with acceptable quality for national variety trials and registration.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Description of the study area

The experiment was conducted in 2020 and 2021 under main season at the Kulumsa Agricultural Research Center (KARC). It lies between 8° 00' and 8° 02' N and 39° 07' and 39° 10' E at an altitude of 2210 m.a.s.l. The research center found in Tiyo District, Arsi Administrative Zone, Oromia Regional State, 167 km southeast of Addis Ababa. KARC is located on gentle terrain with slopes ranging from 0 to 10%, and it has elevations ranging from 1,980 to 2,230 meters above sea level (Abayneh *et al.*, 2003). The agro-climatic conditions of the area are humid, with an average annual rainfall of 832 mm, and have an uneven rainfall regime, with the rainy season lasting from March to September. However, the peak season is from July to August, and the average annual minimum and maximum temperatures are 10°C and 23.20°C, respectively (KARC metrological station, unpublished data). The coldest month is December, and March and May are the hottest months. KARC has three main types of soils: Eutric Verti soil, Vertic Luvi soil, and Vertic Cambi soil (Abayneh *et al.*, 2003).

2.2. Experimental materials and design

Four hundred and fifty black cumin accessions were collected from different parts of Ethiopia and the Ethiopian Biodiversity Institute evaluated under observation nursery at the Kulumsa Agricultural Research Center (KARC) in 2018 and 2019. Based on their agronomic, yield and quality performance, twenty one promising accessions (219971, 90501, 242528, 90503, 9067, 242842, 223071, 90504, 229808, 8502, 22906, 242838, 242844, 230039, 282833, 242323, 9068, 905002, 242826, 9069, and 1069) were selected and evaluated further in a preliminary variety trial in 2020 and 2021. The accessions were evaluated along with one local check and two standard checks (Eden and Silingo). The experiment was laid out in an alpha lattice design, with each accession replicated twice.

Table 1: List of twenty one accessions, one local and two standard checks evaluated for eight morphological characters

S.N	Treatment	Remarks	S.N	Treatments	Remarks
1	219971	Accession	13	8502	Accession
2	90501	Accession	14	22906	Accession
3	242528	Accession	15	242838	Accession
4	90503	Accession	16	242844	Accession
5	Silingo (standard check)	Variety	17	230039	Accession
6	9067	Accession	18	282833	Accession
7	Local check	Local check	19	242323	Accession
8	242842	Accession	20	9068	Accession
9	223071	Accession	21	905002	Accession
10	Eden (standard check)	Variety	22	242826	Accession
11	90504	Accession	23	9069	Accession
12	229808	Accession	24	1069	Accession

The row length of a plot was 2.0 m and 1.8 m width with spacing of 30 cm between rows and 1 m between plots. The four central rows were considered as net plots in which, plant and plot base data recording was conducted. The net plot size of each experimental unit or plot was 2m × 1.2 m = 2.4 m².

2.3. Data collection

2.3.1. Phenological data

2.3.1.1. Days to 50% flowering

Days to 50% flowering were calculated from the sowing date to date at 50% of the plants in a plot were flowered.

2.3.2. Agronomic, yield and yield related data

2.3.2.1. Plant height (cm)

Plant height was measured from the base of the plant to the tip of the pod at harvest. It was taken from five randomly sampled plants and the total was divided by the number of sampled plants to get the average and the average value was used for data analysis.

2.3.2.2 The number of primary branches plant⁻¹

The number of primary branches was recorded by counting primary branches raised from the main stem of five plants. It was taken from five randomly sampled plants and the total was divided by the number of sampled plants to get the average and the average value was used for data analysis.

2.3.2.3 Number of secondary branches plant⁻¹

The number of secondary branches was recorded by counting secondary branches raised from the primary branches of five plants. It was taken from five randomly sampled plants and the total was divided by the number of sampled plants to get the average and the average value was used for data analysis.

2.3.2.4 Number of pod plants⁻¹

The number of pods per plant was recorded by counting all pods of five plants. It was taken from five randomly sampled plants and the total was divided by the number of sampled plants to get the average and the average value was used for data analysis.

2.3.2.5 Number of seed pod⁻¹

The number of seeds per pod was recorded by counting all seeds of five pods. It was taken from five randomly sampled plants and the total was divided by the number of sampled plants to get the average and the average value was used for data analysis.

2.3.2.6 Seed yield (g plant⁻¹)

The average seed weight of five randomly selected plants was weighed and used as seed yield per plant. It was taken from five randomly sampled plants and the total was divided by the number of sampled plants to get the average and the average value was used for data analysis.

2.3.2.7 Seed yield (kg ha⁻¹)

Seed yield per hectare was converted from seed yield obtained from all plants harvested from the net plot and the obtained result was converted to per hectare.

2.4. Statistical analysis

2.4.1. Analysis of Variance

All collected data for each parameter were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) according to the method described in (Gomez and Gomez, 1984) using R software (Anonymous, 2020). Duncan Multiple Range Test was used to compare the mean performance of black cumin accessions at a 5% level of significance.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Analysis of variance

Combined data analysis was performed over the years and the obtained result showed that there was a highly significant ($P < 0.01$) difference among the studied accessions for Days to 50% flowering, Number of primary branches plant⁻¹, Number of secondary branches plant⁻¹, Number of pod plant⁻¹, Number of seed pod⁻¹, Seed yield (g plant⁻¹) and seed yield (kg ha⁻¹) whereas significant difference was recorded for plant height at maturity ($P < 0.05$) (Table 2).

Table 2: Combined mean squares of eight quantitative traits of twenty one black cumin accessions, one local check and two standard checks evaluated at Kulumsa in 2020 and 2021

Traits	Replication (DF=1)	Block (Rep) (D=11)	Year (DF=1)	Source of variation				
				Accessions (DF=23)	Year x Accessions (DF=23)	Error (DF=36)	CV (%)	R ²
				D50%F	15.84	5.29	2.34ns	12.16**
PH	18.55	5.60	0.02ns	11.15*	13.43**	5.19	3.76	0.78
NPBPP	0.12	0.45	54**	0.67**	0.65**	0.18	7.5	0.93
NSBPP	0.00	3.97	66.33**	6.16**	4.95*	2.16	11.23	0.82
NPPP	0.09	8.38	962.67**	19.70**	18.62**	3.51	9.80	0.94
NSPP	28.77	59.44	1967.5**	239.33**	171.63**	27.43	5.26	0.92
SYPP	0.36	0.24	20.97**	0.86**	0.78**	0.09	11.15	0.95
SYPH	1403.66	38504.68	99379.89**	41982.57**	33527.55**	4969.48	9.84	0.93

*: $P=0.05$; **: $P=0.01$; ns: non-significant difference; DF: Degrees of freedom; CV: Coefficient of variation; R²: Relative efficiency; D50%F: Days to 50% flowering; PH: Plant height at maturity (cm); NPBPP: Number of primary branch plant⁻¹; NSBPP: Number of secondary branch plant⁻¹; NPPP: Number of pod plant⁻¹; NSPP: Number of seed pod⁻¹; SYPP: Seed yield plant⁻¹; SYPH: Seed yield hectare⁻¹

3.2 Mean performance of black cumin accessions for phenological data

Combined data analysis was performed over the years, and the analysis of variance showed that there was a highly significant ($P<0.01$) difference among the studied accessions for days to 50% flowering and the mean of days to 50% flowering ranged from 88.75–95.75 days (Table 3). The highest mean of days to 50% flowering was recorded by accession 219971 (95.75 days); followed by accession 90501 (95.25 days) whereas the lowest days to flowering were recorded by accession 1069 (88.75 days) (Table 3). This implies that those accessions that flowered earlier than others can be recommended in low moisture growing areas. Contrary to our results, Assefa and Girma (2016) reported that among evaluated black cumin varieties, all evaluated varieties flowered earlier than our accessions (local variety took 47.73 days to flower whereas Dirshaye, Darbera, and Eden took 50.2, 50.3, and 50.6 days to flower respectively. Supporting results were reported by Bekele and Georgis (2023), and they reported that the local variety took the shortest days to flower (80.83 days) as compared to the improved variety Aden took 95.54 days to flower. Gebremedin et al. (2023) also reported that the days to 50% flowering ranged from 70–99 days, with a mean value of 86.3 days.

3.3 Mean performance black cumin accessions for agronomic, yield and yield related traits

Combined data analysis was performed over the years, and the analysis of variance showed that there was a highly significant ($P<0.01$) difference among the studied accessions for the number of primary branch plant⁻¹, the number of secondary branch plant⁻¹, the number of pod plant⁻¹, the number of seed pod⁻¹, the seed yield plant⁻¹, and the seed yield hectare⁻¹, whereas a significant difference was recorded for plant height at maturity ($P<0.05$) (Table 3). The mean for plant height, number of primary branch plant⁻¹, number of secondary branch plant⁻¹, number of pod plant⁻¹, number of seed pod⁻¹, seed yield plant⁻¹, and seed yield hectare⁻¹ ranged from 57.45–63.85 cm, 4.85–6.4, 10.10–14.70, 14.45–23.05, 87.05–116.75, 1.87–3.5 g⁻¹, and 392.81–881.98 kg ha⁻¹ respectively (Table 3). The highest mean of plant height was recorded by standard check Silingo (63.85 cm), followed by accession 242528 (62.70 cm) and standard check Eden (62.70 cm), whereas the lowest was recorded by accession 282833 (57.45 cm) (Table 3). Supporting results were reported by Demis et al. (2023), who reported that among the evaluated black cumin accessions, the highest mean of plant height was recorded by accessions 242840 (61.02 cm). Contrary to our findings, Assefa and Girma (2016) reported a shorter plant height that ranged from 41.5 cm to 32 cm from improved black cumin varieties.

The highest mean of the primary branch was recorded from accession 9067 (6.4), followed by accession 90501 (6.25) and standard check Eden (6.25). Similarly, the highest mean of the secondary branch was recorded by standard check Silingo (14.75), followed by accessions 9068 (14.70), 242528 (14.60), and standard check Eden (14.60), whereas the lowest was recorded by accession 905002 (10.10). Asefa and Beriso (2020) reported a lower number of primary branches plant⁻¹, which ranged from 4.67 to 3.33 as compared to our results.

Numbers of pod plant⁻¹, number of seed pod⁻¹, seed yield plant⁻¹, and seed yield hectare⁻¹ were studied for yield and yield related parameters. Accordingly, the highest mean of the number of pod plants was recorded by 219971 (23.05) and the

lowest mean was recorded by accession 242528 (14.45). Similarly, the highest mean number of seed pod⁻¹ was recorded by accession 242838 (116.75), followed by standard check Silingo (110.60) and accessions 230039 (109.79), 9068 (108.30), and 90503 (107.85). Asefa and Beriso (2020) reported a lower number of pods plant⁻¹, which ranged from 10.72 to 6.96 as compared to our findings. A supporting result was reported by Demis et al. (2023), who recorded the highest number of pods plant⁻¹ from accession 242840 (21.52). Assefa and Girma (2016) reported a significant difference among varieties in the number of pods plant⁻¹ and according to their findings, the highest number of pods plant⁻¹ was recorded by the Dirshaye variety (16).

Seed yield per plant and seed yield per hectare are the most important yield related parameters for the success of crop improvement. The result of this experiment showed that the highest seed yield plant⁻¹ was recorded by accession 90503 (3.50 g plant⁻¹), followed by accession 219971 (3.45 g plant⁻¹), 8502 (3.25 g plant⁻¹), and 242826 (3.05 g plant⁻¹), whereas the lowest seed yield plant⁻¹ was recorded by accession 282833 (1.87 g plant⁻¹).

The highest seed yield (kg ha⁻¹) was recorded by accession 242528 (881.98 kg ha⁻¹), followed by accessions 8502 (849.17 kg ha⁻¹), 9068 (841.88 kg ha⁻¹), 90501 (835.94 kg ha⁻¹), 223071 (799.79 kg ha⁻¹), 242838 (780.94 kg ha⁻¹), 282833 (768.02 kg ha⁻¹), 242826 (758.02 kg ha⁻¹), 905002 (754.17 kg ha⁻¹), 219971 (748.44 kg ha⁻¹), 90504 (747.60 kg ha⁻¹), and 242842 (743.33 kg ha⁻¹). Based on their seed yield potential, those aforementioned accessions were advanced to the national variety trial. Similarly, the lowest seed yield hectare⁻¹ was recorded by accession 242323 (392.81 kg ha⁻¹). Demis et al. (2023) reported a higher seed yield hectare⁻¹ than our report, and they recorded the highest seed yield from accession 242840 (1102 kg ha⁻¹). Asefa and Beriso (2020) reported the mean seed yield of accessions across the environment ranged from 2454 to 1607 kg ha⁻¹ from fourteen black cumin accessions evaluated against standard checks for two years from 2018 to 2019 at Sinana, Goro, and Gindhir. Compared to our findings, the reported result of seed yield hectare⁻¹ was higher and the observed difference might be due to location and accessions differences. Contrary to our result, from an experiment conducted over multiple locations, Assefa and Girma (2016) reported that among the evaluated black cumin varieties at all locations, the Dirshaye and Eden varieties recorded the highest mean seed yield with 587 kg ha⁻¹ and 547 kg ha⁻¹, respectively and the lower yield reported might be due to genotype and environmental differences. According to the report of Gebremedin et al. (2023), the seed yield hectare⁻¹ ranged from 190–1930 kg ha⁻¹, with a mean of 880 kg ha⁻¹.

Table 3: Mean performances of twenty one accessions, one local check and two standard check of black cumin for eight yield and yield related traits evaluated at Kulumsa in 2020 and 2021

Accessions	Traits							
	DF	PH	NPBPP	NSBPP	NPPP	NSPP	SYPP	SYPH
219971	95.75 ^a	60.80 ^{a-f}	5.65 ^{b-f}	13.00 ^{abc}	23.05 ^a	100.15 ^{c-e}	3.45 ^{ab}	748.44 ^{bcd}
90501	95.25 ^a	62.05 ^{abc}	6.25 ^{ab}	13.55 ^{abc}	21.80 ^{abc}	95.05 ^{e-i}	2.90 ^{c-f}	835.94 ^{ab}
242528	94.00 ^{ab}	62.70 ^{ab}	6.10 ^{a-d}	14.60 ^a	14.45 ⁱ	103.65 ^{b-e}	2.13 ^{ijk}	881.98 ^a
90503	93.50 ^{abc}	61.40 ^{a-e}	5.50 ^{c-g}	13.10 ^{abc}	19.48 ^{b-f}	107.85 ^{bcd}	3.50 ^a	680.83 ^{cde}
Silingo	93.50 ^{abc}	63.85 ^a	5.90 ^{a-e}	14.75 ^a	20.30 ^{a-d}	110.60 ^{ab}	3.12 ^{a-d}	676.77 ^{de}
9067	92.75 ^{bcd}	57.70 ^{ef}	6.40 ^a	14.40 ^a	17.05 ^{e-i}	95.73 ^{e-i}	2.38 ^{g-j}	670.00 ^{de}
Local check	92.00 ^{b-e}	59.45 ^{b-f}	5.55 ^{b-g}	13.60 ^{ab}	22.05 ^{ab}	93.20 ^{f-i}	3.21 ^{abc}	678.54 ^{de}
242842	92.00 ^{b-e}	62.15 ^{abc}	5.95 ^{a-e}	13.55 ^{abc}	19.93 ^{b-e}	95.15 ^{e-i}	2.99 ^{b-e}	743.33 ^{bcd}
223071	92.00 ^{b-e}	60.80 ^{a-f}	5.65 ^{b-f}	13.25 ^{abc}	19.35 ^{b-f}	89.80 ^{hi}	2.91 ^{cde}	799.79 ^{abc}
Eden	92.00 ^{b-e}	62.70 ^{ab}	6.25 ^{ab}	14.60 ^a	21.65 ^{abc}	97.48 ^{c-h}	2.90 ^{c-f}	667.29 ^{de}
90504	91.75 ^{b-e}	60.00 ^{a-f}	6.20 ^{abc}	13.30 ^{abc}	21.00 ^{abc}	90.75 ^{ghi}	2.85 ^{c-g}	747.60 ^{bcd}
229808	91.25 ^{c-f}	58.30 ^{c-f}	5.15 ^{efg}	11.45 ^{bcd}	18.65 ^{c-h}	100.25 ^{c-f}	2.22 ^{h-k}	613.23 ^e
8502	91.25 ^{c-f}	60.75 ^{a-f}	5.55 ^{b-g}	13.15 ^{abc}	19.78 ^{b-e}	91.01 ^{ghi}	3.25 ^{abc}	849.17 ^{ab}
22906	91.25 ^{c-f}	60.55 ^{a-f}	5.60 ^{b-f}	13.15 ^{abc}	21.00 ^{abc}	108.8 ^{ab}	2.70 ^{d-h}	586.46 ^e
242838	91.00 ^{c-f}	61.75 ^{a-d}	5.75 ^{a-f}	13.00 ^{abc}	19.00 ^{b-g}	116.75 ^a	2.31 ^{h-k}	780.94 ^{a-d}
242844	90.75 ^{d-ef}	58.10 ^{def}	5.60 ^{b-f}	13.15 ^{abc}	19.25 ^{b-g}	99.25 ^{efg}	2.54 ^{e-i}	678.44 ^{de}
230039	90.75 ^{def}	60.95 ^{a-f}	5.30 ^{efg}	13.75 ^{ab}	16.58 ^{f-i}	109.79 ^{ab}	2.42 ^{f-j}	685.94 ^{cde}

282833	90.50 ^{def}	57.45 ^f	5.55 ^{b-g}	11.30 ^{bcd}	15.75 ^{hi}	102.10 ^{b-e}	1.87 ^k	768.02 ^{a-d}
242323	90.50 ^{def}	60.00 ^{a-f}	5.90 ^{a-e}	13.70 ^{ab}	17.35 ^{d-i}	87.05 ⁱ	2.29 ^{h-k}	392.81 ^f
9068	90.50 ^{def}	59.75 ^{b-f}	5.40 ^{d-g}	14.70 ^a	20.55 ^{abc}	108.30 ^{bc}	2.65 ^{d-h}	841.88 ^{ab}
905002	90.25 ^{def}	61.20 ^{a-f}	5.10 ^{fg}	10.10 ^d	17.20 ^{d-i}	89.90 ^{hi}	2.24 ^{h-k}	754.17 ^{bcd}
242826	89.50 ^{ef}	59.40 ^{b-f}	4.85 ^g	11.50 ^{bcd}	19.90 ^{b-e}	98.35 ^{e-h}	3.05 ^{a-d}	758.02 ^{bcd}
9069	89.50 ^{ef}	59.75 ^{b-f}	5.10 ^{fg}	11.05 ^{cd}	16.15 ^{hig}	99.40 ^{d-g}	1.96 ^{jk}	664.90 ^{de}
1069	88.75 ^f	62.30 ^{ab}	5.35 ^{e-g}	12.25 ^{a-d}	17.25 ^{d-i}	97.80 ^{e-h}	2.37 ^{g-j}	692.71 ^{cde}
Mean	91.68	60.58	5.65	13.08	19.1	99.51	2.67	716.55

DF: Days to 50% flowering; PH: Plant height at maturity (cm); NPBPP: Number of primary branch per plant; NSBPP: Number of secondary branch per plant; NPPP: Number of pod per plant; NSPP: Number of seed per pod; SYPP: Seed yield per plant (g plant⁻¹); SYPH: Seed yield per hectare (kg ha⁻¹)

4. Conclusion

Combined analysis of variance showed there were highly significant ($P < 0.01$) differences among the accessions for all recorded parameters except plant height ($P < 0.05$). Twelve accessions recorded mean seed yield from 743.33 to 881.98 kg ha⁻¹, whereas standard checks, Eden and Silingo, recorded 667.29 and 670 kg ha⁻¹, respectively. Therefore, these twelve accessions could be advanced to a national variety trial. Then two to three outperformed accessions could be advanced for a variety verification trial, and they will be released as improved varieties.

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